

A Rare Presentation of Giant Cell Tumor of Bone with Suspected Pericardial and Pulmonary Metastases in a Young Female: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: This case report highlights a rare manifestation of a giant cell tumor of bone in a 16-year-old female, demonstrating unusual pulmonary and pericardial metastases. It typically presents with localized pain and swelling in long bone epiphyseal ends but can exhibit malignant potential and metastasis, notably to the lungs.

Methods and Materials: The patient, previously diagnosed with a giant cell tumor of bone in the lower limb, sought medical attention due to acute shortness of breath and chest pain. Diagnostic imaging revealed multifocal pulmonary nodules and a substantial left-sided pericardial mass, unusual for a giant cell tumor of bone. Chemotherapy with denosumab was initiated as part of the treatment plan.

Results: The case illustrates an uncommon metastatic pattern involving both the lungs and pericardium. Despite initial instability and respiratory distress, the patient showed improvement with supportive care and antibiotics, stabilizing oxygen levels at room air. However, essential diagnostic procedures like echocardiography and pericardial biopsy were delayed, impacting further treatment decisions.

Conclusion: This case underscores the challenging nature of a giant cell tumor of bone, emphasizing the need for a comprehensive multidisciplinary approach for timely diagnosis and intervention, especially in cases displaying uncommon metastatic patterns. Ongoing research is essential to deepen our comprehension of this intricate tumor, enabling the development of more precise treatment approaches that can lead to better outcomes for patients.

Keywords: Giant Cell Tumor; Granulomatous lesions; Hypersensitivity

INTRODUCTION

Giant cell tumor of bone (GCTOB) is an infrequent, generally benign tumor affecting the epiphyseal ends of long bones^[1]. Initially described in the early 19th century, GCTOB was later recognized for its potential for malignant transformation and metastasis^[1,2]. It represents approximately 5% of all primary and 20% of benign bone tumors, with a higher incidence among the Chinese population^[2,3]. Typically manifesting in the third to fourth decades of life and slightly more prevalent in females, GCTOB's clinical presentation varies with the tumor's location^[1,2]. Benign GCTOB commonly presents with localized pain and swelling, while the malignant form may manifest nonspecific symptoms due to distant metastases^[2,3]. Metastases usually affect the lungs, bones, skin, and lymph nodes^[2-4]. In this specific case, the patient presented with chest pain and shortness of breath, symptoms attributed to pericardial and pulmonary involvement as revealed by investigations^[5].

Sustained research is vital to advance our comprehension of this complicated tumor, allowing for the creation of more precise treatment approaches and ultimately enhancing the well-being of patients^[5]. This unique case report presents a rare and ultimately fatal occurrence of GCTOB in a 16-year-old female, highlighting its atypical metastatic pattern involving the pericardium and lungs. This report aims to shed light on this extraordinary case, emphasizing the challenges and nuances associated with diagnosing and managing such atypical presentations of GCTOB. Additionally, we aim to underscore the critical importance of early diagnosis and intervention to improve patient outcomes and prognosis in cases demonstrating uncommon metastatic behavior.

CASE PRESENTATION

We report a rare and unfortunate case of a 16-year-old female diagnosed with GCTOB with pulmonary and suspected pericardial metastases. The patient had a history of right knee pain and swelling for six months, which prompted her to seek medical attention. She received many conservative treatments but did not get relief. She

underwent many investigations, which further indicated bone biopsy. A biopsy sample obtained during curettage and cementing of the right knee region confirmed GCTOB involving the distal femur and proximal tibia. Histopathology of the specimen revealed multinucleated giant cells resembling osteoclasts in a stromal cell background (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Biopsy showing giant cells in bone stromal tissue.

The patient was started on chemotherapy with denosumab 120 mg every fourth week, which is a monoclonal antibody that targets receptor activator of nuclear factor kappa B ligand (RANKL) and inhibits osteoclast formation and activity, thereby reducing bone destruction and inducing tumor regression. However, she complained of cough and chest pain during her follow-up appointment after the surgical procedure. A chest X-ray (CXR) revealed bilateral multifocal pulmonary lesions suggestive of metastatic disease (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Chest X-ray shows bilateral pulmonary metastatic nodules.

The patient's condition worsened over the next two days, leading to emergency department admission due to severe chest pain and shortness of breath. She was vitally unstable, with peripheral oxygen saturation (SPO₂) of 72 percent on room air. On general physical examination, she displayed critical symptoms, such as clubbing of fingers, pallor, peripheral cyanosis, and fever. She had bilateral dull percussion notes, reduced air entry, and a pericardial friction rub on chest examination. The blood examinations revealed an increased white blood cell count (WBC) of 12860 per microliter and a lower hemoglobin (Hb) level of 9 grams per deciliter. Results of liver function tests (LFTs), renal function tests (RFTs), and additional laboratory assessments were within normal range. A pulmonary consultation recommended a CT chest with intravenous contrast, which reported innumerable pulmonary nodules of variable sizes and shapes throughout bilateral lung fields. Additionally, a unique large, enhancing, lobulated left-sided pericardial nodal mass suggesting possible metastasis of GCTOB was reported.

Figure 3. HRCT chest pulmonary lesions and pericardial nodal mass can be appreciated

Repeat X-ray of the right femur was repeated. X-ray of the right knee showed well-circumscribed destructive lesions surrounded by a white rim of bone in the distal femur and an eccentric-looking lytic lesion of the proximal tibia (Figure 4).

Figure 4. X-ray showing osteolytic circumscribed lesion of distal femur surrounded by a rim of white bone. The proximal tibia shows an eccentric-looking destructive lesion.

The patient received initial emergency supportive care, including intravenous fluids and supplemental oxygen via nasal cannula at a rate of two liters per minute. Her condition improved gradually, and she maintained normal oxygen saturation at room air. Despite proper counseling, the parents insisted on discharging the patient on request. Although echocardiography and pericardial biopsy were recommended before discharge for further planning of metastasectomy, the patient passed away later after losing contact.

This case report presents an unusual manifestation of GCTOB with pulmonary and pericardial metastases in a young female patient. It also highlights the challenges in diagnosing and treating this complex tumor. It underscores the need for thorough investigations and early interventions and emphasizes the need for further research to understand the biology and behavior of GCTOB better and refine optimal management strategies.

DISCUSSION

GCTOB, generally considered a locally aggressive benign bone tumor, rarely displays metastatic capacity^[1-5]. Predominantly affecting the epiphysis and adjacent metaphysis of long bones, GCTOB often manifests around the knee^[6,7]. Histologically characterized by multinucleated giant cells in a stromal cell background, the pathogenesis of GCTOB is not fully elucidated^[8]. However, it is believed that neoplastic stromal cells overexpress RANKL, stimulating the recruitment and activation of osteoclast-like giant cells, causing bone resorption and tumor expansion^[9,10].

GCTOB has a higher incidence among Asian populations and typically occurs between 20 and 40, with a slight predilection for females^[1-4]. Clinical presentation varies based on tumor location, with localized pain and swelling being common symptoms, often leading to pathological fractures due to mechanical deficiency resulting from local bone disruption^[11]. Distant metastasis is observed in approximately 1 to 9 percent of patients, most frequently affecting the lungs^[12]. Pulmonary metastasis in GCTOB can present with dyspnea and chest pain, underlining the potential of GCT for systemic spread impacting patient prognosis and management plans^[13-15].

Various imaging modalities, including x-rays, CT scans, and MRI, aid in GCTOB diagnosis, providing information about the tumor's size, shape, location, extent, relationship with adjacent structures, signs of malignancy, or metastasis^[14,15]. In the reported case, imaging studies revealed a large tumor in the right knee, bilateral diffuse lung lesions, and a unique pericardial nodular mass, suggesting metastasis of GCT^[15,16]. Although mediastinal metastasis in GCTOB is exceedingly rare, the peculiar findings of combined pulmonary and pericardial involvement have not been previously reported.

Treatment of GCT depends on the tumor site, extent, and presence of metastasis^[13,14]. Surgery is the preferred treatment for localized GCTOB, involving curettage, resection, or amputation. In cases of metastasis, a multidisciplinary approach is vital, engaging medical oncologists, radiation oncologists, orthopedic surgeons,

and cardiothoracic surgeons^[13,14]. Treatment options, such as chemotherapy, radiotherapy, and surgical metastasectomy, can be tailored to individual needs^[15]. While no highly effective chemotherapeutic agent is available, denosumab is commonly used to treat unresectable GCTOB^[14]. However, it has limitations and adverse effects, necessitating cautious use and close monitoring^[14].

This case report highlights an unusual GCTOB manifestation with pulmonary and pericardial metastases. It underscores the challenges in diagnosing and managing this complex tumor, emphasizing the need for comprehensive evaluation, timely intervention, and further research to comprehend the tumor's biology and behavior, refining optimal management strategies.

LIMITATIONS

This single-case report explores a unique instance of giant cell tumor of bone (GCTOB) in a 16-year-old female with atypical pulmonary and suspected pericardial metastases. However, the study has limitations, including its singular case focus, hindering a comprehensive view of GCTOB. Diagnostic constraints, due to the patient's instability, prevent a confirmed pericardial metastasis diagnosis. Long-term follow-up, alternative treatment exploration, genetic analysis, and broader demographic representation were lacking, limiting the study's scope and generalizability. Addressing these limitations through further research and collaborative efforts is vital for enhancing GCTOB understanding and advancing diagnostic and therapeutic strategies.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this case report underscores a rare occurrence of metastatic GCTOB with unique pericardial involvement in a young female. It accentuates the aggressive nature of GCTOB and the importance of considering metastasis in patients displaying atypical symptoms. Despite its rarity, further research is imperative to gather additional data and enhance comprehension of the causes, pathophysiology, diagnostic modalities, prognosis, and management strategies. Collaborative efforts among medical professionals and researchers are vital to exploring and developing standardized treatment guidelines for GCTOB with metastasis, ultimately improving patient outcomes.

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